

Molar Volume of Mercuric Chloride and Cupric Chloride in Water and Aqueous Solutions of Dextrose

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The apparent molar volume (ϕ_v) of mercuric chloride and cupric chloride has been determined in water and 5, 10, 15 and 20% aqueous dextrose solutions at different temperatures. Results have been interpreted in terms of solute-solute and solute-solvent interactions, and structure-making/structure-breaking capacity from ($\delta^2\phi_v/\delta T^2$) values. The apparent molar expansibility has also been determined. Mercuric chloride and cupric chloride have been found to be structure-maker in water. Mercuric chloride has been found as structure-breaker and cupric chloride as the structure-maker in aqueous dextrose solutions.

The study of apparent molar volumes of electrolytes at infinite dilution and their dependence on temperature can furnish useful information on the nature of solute-solvent interactions¹. In the recent years, an increasing interest has been shown in the study of electrolytes in aqueous and aqueous carbohydrate solutions² with a view to investigate solute-solvent interactions under varied conditions.

Dextrose is present in biofluids and it is commonly taken by all living beings in one form or the other. Increasing concern over the toxicity of heavy metals in the environment has led to increase research activity to identify the fate of these metal ions in the organisms. The study of toxic salts like mercuric chloride and cupric chloride solutions in water and aqueous dextrose was carried to understand the nature of solute-solvent and solute-solute interactions, by measuring the density and molar volume of their solutions.

Results and Discussion

The apparent molar volume of mercuric chloride and cupric chloride in water and aqueous dextrose solutions have been calculated from density data by using equation (1)³,

$$\phi_v = \frac{M_2}{d^0} - \frac{1000(d - d^0)}{m d^0} \quad (1)$$

where d^0 is the density of solvent, d the density of solution, m the molality of solution and M_2 the molecular weight of the salt. Errors in ϕ_v were calculated from equation (2)⁴,

$$\Delta\phi_v = (2 \Delta d/d^2)(1000/m + M_2) \quad (2)$$

Equation (2) assumes error to be associated with the density of solution (d) and solvent (d^0). Moreover, errors associated with determination of solution concentration are not the limiting factor while calculating the apparent molar volumes. The error as derived from equation (2) was estimated to range from $\pm 0.06 \text{ cm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1}$ at 0.01*m* concentration to $\pm 0.10 \text{ cm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1}$ at 0.10*m* concentration. The densities of various solutions of HgCl_2 and CuCl_2 in water and aqueous dextrose are found to obey Root's equation,

$$d = d^0 + AC - BC^{3/2} \quad (2B)$$

The magnitude of constants A and B (Table 1) depends upon the nature of solute and solvent. The validity of equation (2B) justifies the use of Masson's equation (3) for the estimation of the limiting apparent molar volume,

$$\phi_v = \phi_v^0 + S_v \sqrt{c} \quad (3)$$

where ϕ_v^0 and S_v are calculated from the intercept

TABLE I—VALUES OF ϕ_V^0 , S_V , ϕ_E^0 , $\Delta\phi_{V(\text{excess})}^0$ AND ROOT'S EQUATION PARAMETERS (A , B) FOR MERCURIC CHLORIDE AND CUPRIC CHLORIDE IN WATER AND AQUEOUS DEXTROSE AT DIFFERENT TEMPERATURES

Temp. K	System wt.% dextrose	ϕ_V^0 $\text{cm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1}$	S_V $\text{cm}^3 \text{lit}^{1/2} \text{mol}^{-3/2}$	ϕ_E^0 $\text{cm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1} \text{K}^{-1}$	$\Delta\phi_{V(\text{excess})}^0$	A $\text{g lit mol}^{-1} \text{cm}^{-3}$	B $\text{g lit}^{3/2} \text{mol}^{3/2} \text{cm}^{-3}$
<i>Mercuric chloride :</i>							
303	0	122.37 ± 0.06	-114.47	-4.12	-	0.150	0.111
308	0	105.33 ± 0.08	-177.00	-2.70	-	0.168	0.175
313	0	95.37 ± 0.08	-179.97	-1.28	-	0.177	0.174
318	0	92.99 ± 0.09	-235.74	+0.13	-	0.179	0.236
303	5	149.53 ± 0.07	-234.10	-5.40	27.16	0.118	0.240
308	5	116.43 ± 0.06	-137.41	-7.84	11.10	0.153	0.144
313	5	71.10 ± 0.07	68.91	-10.29	-24.76	0.199	-0.066
318	5	14.59 ± 0.08	204.52	-12.73	-78.40	0.259	-0.222
303	10	143.45 ± 0.08	-238.86	-5.42	21.09	0.123	0.246
308	10	109.24 ± 0.08	-134.50	-8.27	3.91	0.159	0.139
313	10	60.74 ± 0.07	85.49	-11.13	-34.63	0.209	-0.083
318	10	3.15 ± 0.09	212.07	-13.98	-89.83	0.269	-0.218
303	15	135.06 ± 0.08	-227.01	-1.32	12.69	0.129	0.241
308	15	112.39 ± 0.08	-178.26	-7.75	7.06	0.154	0.187
313	15	57.61 ± 0.09	66.56	-14.17	-37.75	0.211	-0.066
318	15	-7.63 ± 0.09	209.90	-20.59	-100.61	0.280	-0.218
303	20	121.07 ± 0.07	-200.57	-2.36	-1.30	0.153	0.177
308	20	97.25 ± 0.08	-141.58	-7.16	-8.07	0.169	0.148
313	20	49.44 ± 0.08	64.01	-11.96	-45.93	0.219	-0.066
318	20	-19.25 ± 0.09	229.64	-16.76	-112.29	0.291	-0.242
<i>Cupric chloride :</i>							
303	0	24.57 ± 0.09	86.55	-2.28	-	0.146	-0.085
308	0	13.37 ± 0.09	102.17	-2.20	-	0.157	-0.102
313	0	11.04 ± 0.09	84.99	-2.13	-	0.159	-0.081
318	0	0.57 ± 0.10	94.58	-2.06	-	0.169	-0.088
303	5	54.31 ± 0.07	62.27	-1.99	29.74	0.115	-0.065
308	5	46.92 ± 0.07	80.56	-0.96	33.54	0.123	-0.081
313	5	44.66 ± 0.08	65.52	+0.06	33.62	0.126	-0.067
318	5	41.25 ± 0.08	61.93	+1.09	40.68	0.129	-0.074
303	10	39.57 ± 0.07	78.64	-1.13	14.99	0.128	-0.074
308	10	35.28 ± 0.08	79.02	-0.59	21.91	0.135	-0.083
313	10	33.71 ± 0.09	63.31	-0.04	22.67	0.137	-0.067
318	10	29.49 ± 0.08	66.05	+0.50	28.92	0.140	-0.065
303	15	31.08 ± 0.08	64.49	-1.18	6.51	0.138	-0.066
308	15	26.16 ± 0.08	75.14	-0.79	12.78	0.143	-0.075
313	15	23.15 ± 0.08	28.68	-0.41	12.12	0.147	-0.071
318	15	18.65 ± 0.08	71.51	-0.03	18.08	0.151	-0.074
303	20	20.95 ± 0.09	63.38	-1.54	-3.62	0.149	-0.072
308	20	15.10 ± 0.09	70.09	-0.80	1.72	0.152	-0.069
313	20	12.93 ± 0.09	68.72	-0.06	1.89	0.157	-0.072
318	20	11.06 ± 0.09	59.55	+0.67	10.48	0.160	-0.068

and slope of plots of ϕ_v vs \sqrt{c} . The values of limiting molar volume and slopes are recorded in Table 1.

ϕ_v^0 is a measure of solute-solvent interactions. ϕ_v^0 values of mercuric chloride solutions in water are higher than those of cupric chloride solutions and also in 5, 10, 15 and 20 percent aqueous dextrose at temperatures 303, 308 and 313 K. At temperature 318 K, ϕ_v^0 values, i.e. solute-solvent interactions for mercuric chloride were observed much less than cupric chloride in 5, 10, 15 and 20% aqueous dextrose solutions. ϕ_v^0 values of HgCl_2 and CuCl_2 solutions in different compositions (5, 10, 15, 20 wt%) of dextrose show that solute-solvent interactions decrease with increase in the concentration of dextrose in aqueous media at 303, 308, 313 and 318 K. The molecular interactions in the solvent system increase due to the extensive hydrogen bonding amongst the solvent molecules and consequently solute-solvent interactions decrease. The limiting apparent molar volume (ϕ_v^0) decreases with increase in temperature for HgCl_2 and CuCl_2 solutions in water and aqueous dextrose. The decrease in the ϕ_v^0 values with increasing temperature may be attributed to the increase in solvation.

The values of S_v found positive for CuCl_2 in water and 5, 10, 15, 20 wt% aqueous dextrose solutions suggest strong ion-ion interaction⁵ at temperatures 303, 308, 313 and 318 K. In case of HgCl_2 , negative S_v values in water and 5, 10, 15 and 20 wt% aqueous dextrose solutions at temperatures 303 and 308 K, confirm the absence of ion-ion interactions. At temperatures 313 and 318 K, high positive values for S_v in aqueous dextrose suggest strong ion-ion interactions. The temperature dependence of ϕ_v^0 of mercuric chloride in water (equation 4) and 5% dextrose (equation 5) can be expressed by the equations,

$$[\phi_v^0] \text{ cm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} = 373.362 - 12.6163t + 0.1417t^2 \quad (4)$$

$$[\phi_v^0] \text{ cm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} = 91.508 + 9.266t - 0.24442t^2 \quad (5)$$

where t is the temperature (K). The equations showing temperature dependence of ϕ_v^0 of cupric chloride in water and 15% dextrose are shown in equations (6) and (7) respectively,

$$[\phi_v^0] \text{ cm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} = 277.735 - 13.753t + 0.17714t^2 \quad (6)$$

$$[\phi_v^0] \text{ cm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} = 100.86 - 3.4763t + 0.3834t^2 \quad (7)$$

The apparent molar expansibility, $\phi_E^0 = (\partial^2 \phi_v^0 / \partial t^2)$ calculated from equation (3) for HgCl_2 , has been found to increase with temperature (Table 1). The increase of ϕ_E^0 with temperature for mercuric chloride in water shows caging effect⁶. HgCl_2 shows reverse behaviour in aqueous dextrose solutions. In case of CuCl_2 , ϕ_E^0 increases with increase in temperature (Table 2) in water and 5, 10, 15, 20 wt% aqueous dextrose solutions suggesting caging effect⁶. The structure-making/breaking capacity of mercuric chloride and cupric chloride may be interpreted with the help of Hepler's reasoning⁷, i.e. on the basis of sign $(\partial/\partial T^2)_p$. It has been shown from general thermodynamic equation (8),

$$[\partial \bar{C}_p^0 / \partial p]_T = -T[\partial^2 \phi_v^0 / \partial T^2]_p \quad (8)$$

where \bar{C}_p^0 is the partial molal heat capacity at infinite dilution. From equation (8) it is clear that a structure-making electrolyte should have a positive values of $(\partial^2 \phi_v^0 / \partial T^2)_p$. In case of HgCl_2 in water the sign of this term is found to be positive and hence acts as structure-maker in water. In aqueous dextrose, the value has been found to be negative and hence HgCl_2 acts as structure-breaker. For CuCl_2 in water and aqueous dextrose solutions the value of this term was found positive which shows that CuCl_2 acts as structure-maker both in water and aqueous dextrose.

The limiting excess molar volume of CuCl_2 and HgCl_2 for different compositions of dextrose have been estimated from equation (9),

$$\Delta \phi_v^0 (\text{excess}) = \phi_v^0 (\text{AB in dextrose}) - \phi_v^0 (\text{AB in water}) \quad (9)$$

where AB represent the electrolyte under study. $\Delta\phi_{v(\text{excess})}^0$ (Table 1) for HgCl_2 decreases with increase in concentration of dextrose, and it also decreases with increase in temperature.

$\Delta\phi_{v(\text{excess})}^0$ (Table 1) for CuCl_2 decreases with increase in concentration of dextrose and increases with increase in temperature. The positive values of $\Delta\phi_{v(\text{excess})}^0$ values for HgCl_2 at temperatures 303 and 308 K suggest that solvation of HgCl_2 in aqueous dextrose is more than that in water, but at 313 and 318 K negative values reveal that solvation of mercuric chloride is more in water than in aqueous dextrose solutions. $\Delta\phi_{v(\text{excess})}^0$ values for CuCl_2 indicate that the solvation of CuCl_2 in aqueous dextrose is more than that in water.

Experimental

Water used for solutions had specific conductance in the range $0.1\text{--}1.0 \times 10^{-6} \Omega^{-1} \text{cm}^{-1}$. Mercuric chloride, cupric chloride and dextrose (all AnalaR) were dried over anhydrous calcium chloride for more than 48 h and used as such. All the solutions were prepared by weight and conversion of molality to molarity was done by

using the standard expression⁸. The concentration range of HgCl_2 and CuCl_2 in water and aqueous dextrose was 0.01 to 0.1 m. Density was determined as described by Ward and Millero⁹ in a water-bath ($\pm 0.05^\circ$).

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